

Studies on some Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Palladium(II) Complexes with Naphthol Derivatives

Y. M. ISSA*, M. S. RIZK, N. T. ABDEL-GHANI and S. M. ATWA
Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt

Manuscript received 9 July 1992, revised 16 April 1993, accepted 15 June 1993

Nitrosonaphthols are widely used as analytical reagents, and they are capable of forming chelates with a number of transition metal ions¹. 1- and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids have been determined potentiometrically in non-aqueous solvents². 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid was used for the spectrophotometric determination³ of Fe^{III} at pH 2–5 and U^{VI} at pH 4–6. Aromatic nitroso compounds were determined with transition elements in glycerol using amperometric and potentiometric methods⁴. The method was found selective and the relative error was less than 3%. The present investigated deals with the use of some nitroso- and non-nitrosonaphthol derivatives as chelating agents for the divalent Co, Ni, Cu and Pd ions.

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis were found to be in a good agreement with those required by the tentative structures. In all cases, the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) solid complexes could be isolated.

The infrared spectra of solid chelates display interesting changes which may give a reasonable idea about the structure of these chelates. The broadness of the band at 3 500 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the water molecules coordinated to the central metal ions as confirmed by the TGA. All the ligands (1–4) show bands at 1 220–1 200 and 1 130–1 110 cm⁻¹ due to the δ_{OH} modes. The splitting of the former and

the shift of the latter to higher wave number in the spectra of the chelates indicate deprotonation of the phenolic OH of the naphthalene nucleus and participation of the OH in chelation. The nitroso –N=O bands observed at 1 410–1 400 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of N1 HNA (3) and N3 HNA (4) show no change in the spectra of the complexes, which indicate that the NO group does not participate in chelation. The bands at 1 630 and 1 660 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of 1,2 HNA (1), 3,2 HNA (2), N1 HNA (3) and N3 HNA (4) derivatives which are assigned to C=O stretching of the carboxylic group, disappeared in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the participation of the COOH group in chelation with the metal ion.

The ir spectra of the metal complexes show a band at 595–620 cm⁻¹ which is characteristic of M ← O dative bond⁵, resulting from the interaction between carboxylic and hydroxylic oxygen atoms with central metal ion. This band is not obviously present in the spectra of the free ligands.

The TG of some of the metal chelates were performed and the weight-loss of each chelate was calculated (Table 1) and used for the calculation of the number of water molecules attached to each metal ion. The loss below 100° is attributed to the moisture and hygroscopic water, since some of the chelates are hygroscopic in nature. For 1 : 1 Cu^{II}–N1 HNA and Cu^{II}–N3 HNA chelates, two water molecules are coordinated

TABLE 1—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS DATA OF SOLID CHELATES OF SOME OF THE METAL COMPLEXES

Complex (M : L)	Hygroscopic water			Coordinate water			% metallic residue Found/ (Calcd.)
	Temp. °C upto	Weight loss(%) Found/ (Calcd.)	No. of water molecules	Temp. range °C	Weight loss(%) Found/ (Calcd.)	No. of water molecules	
Cu-C (1 : 1) [Cu(C ₁₁ H ₅ O ₄ N).2H ₂ O].H ₂ O	120	5.00 (5.41)	1	120–200	11.30 (10.83)	2	23.33 (23.91)
Co-D (1 : 2) [Co(C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₈ N ₂).2H ₂ O].6H ₂ O	120	16.67 (17.01)	6	120–200	6.10 (5.67)	2	12.34 (11.80)
Ni-D (1 : 1) [Ni(C ₁₁ H ₅ O ₄ N).4H ₂ O].5H ₂ O	120	21.33 (20.65)	5	120–325	15.33 (16.53)	4	17.24 (17.14)
Ni-D (1 : 2) Ni(C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₈ N ₂).2H ₂ O].5H ₂ O	100	14.67 (14.59)	5	100–200	6.10 (5.84)	2	12.67 (12.11)
Pd-A (1 : 2) [Pd(C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₆).2H ₂ O]	–	–	–	200	7.14 (6.97)	2	14.29 (23.70)

to the metal ion to fulfil the coordination number four, and they are expelled within the temperature range 120–200°. In 1 : 1 M-N1 HNA, M-N3 HNA (M = Co^{II} and Ni^{II}), M-1,3 HNA and M-3,2 HNA (M = Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}) chelates, four water molecules are coordinated to the metal ion fulfil the coordination number six, and they are expelled within the temperature range 120–325°. In 1 : 2 M-N1 HNA, M-N3 HNA (M = Co^{II} and Ni^{II}), M-1,2 HNA and M-3,2 HNA (M = Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}) chelates, there are two coordinated water molecules and they are expelled at 120–200° (Table 1). The final stage of the TG curves represents the percent of metallic residue in the form of metal oxide. The results were found to be in good agreement with the theoretical values and with those obtained by determination of the metal ion after decomposition of the chelate applying the reported method⁶, and with the results of the elemental analysis, except that in case of Pd-chelates, the residue was less than calculated values due to partial volatility at such high temperature.

The DTA curves are characterised by the presence of one endothermic peak in the temperature range 50–200° due to elimination of

water molecules. At temperature above 250°, an exothermic peak attributed to a phase change was observed which is due to the change in crystal structure of the complex. Above this temperature decomposition and combustion started followed by decarbonisation of the organic material in presence of oxygen, and finally metal oxide was left.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of the highest purity available. Triple-distilled water was used. The following ligands were used : 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (1,2 HNA) (1), 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (3,2 HNA) (2) (both B.D.H.), 4-nitroso-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (N1 HNA) (3) and 4-nitroso-3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (N3 HNA) (4).

Ligands 3 and 4 were prepared by nitrosation of the parent compounds 1 and 2 as reported earlier⁷. Stock solutions of the ligands (1–4; 1×10^{-3} M) were prepared in ethanol. The 10^{-3} M solutions of metal ions Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} were prepared and standardised complexometrically. The solid chelates were prepared by

NOTE

mixing hot saturated ethanolic solutions of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} ion (0.005 mol) with the requisite amount of the ligands (1-4) sufficient to form 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 complex. The solid complexes separated on standing were washed with water and ethanol and kept in vacuum desiccator. All the complexes were subjected to elemental analysis and their metal ions content was determined after decomposition using H_2SO_4 and hydrogen peroxide then titrated with EDTA⁸, and their structures were confirmed by ir spectroscopy.

The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. The thermogravimetric analysis (TG) was done using a OD 102 MOM thermal analyser (Budapest). The weight-loss was measured from ambient temperature up to 900° at a heating rate of 10° per min.

References

1. S. A. BAJUE, T. P. DASGUPTA and G. C. LALOR, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 431; D. G. MARATHE, R. S. AMBULKAR and K. N. MUNSHI, *Natl. Acad. Sci. Lett. (India)*, 1984, **7**, 153; R. PETROLA and O. MAKITIE, *Soum. Kemistilehti*, 1973, **10**, 46 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **78**, 102624); W. JEDRZEJEWSKI and W. KLAJS, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1982, **27**, 199; S. MOTOMIZU and K. TOEI, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 89.
2. L. N. BYKOVA, S. T. RASHEVSKAYA, N. A. TAZARYA and E. S. RUBSTOVA, *Zav. Lab.*, 1965, **31**, 415.
3. S. SARVAGYA and V. B. S. CHANHAN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 149; A. N. PANT, R. N. SONI and S. L. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3302.
4. E. RUZICKA, M. PALESKOVA and J. A. JILEK, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1980, **45**, 1677.
5. M. A. DAVID, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", Edward Arnold, London, 1967, p. 235.
6. A. M. G. MACDONALD and P. SIVICHANYA, *Microchem. J.*, 1969, **14**, 199.
7. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA, F. A. AMER and M. A. KHATTAB, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **14**, 713.
8. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediamine-tetraacetic Acid", D. Von Norstand, Princeton, 1958.

